

THE INFLUENCE OF ONLINE REVIEWS AND RATINGS ON CONSUMER PURCHASE DECISIONS OF ELECTRONIC ACCESSORIES

¹Navika Jain, ²Prof. Parveen Kaur Lamba, ^{3*}Dr. Mansi Bansal

¹B.Com. Hons., 4th Year | Roll No. 2022BCH1032, Sri Guru Tegh Bahadur Khalsa College, University of Delhi, Email: navikajain13@gmail.com

²Associate Professor, Sri Guru Tegh Bahadur Khalsa College, University of Delhi
Email: parveenklamba@sgtbkhalsa.du.ac.in

³Associate Professor, Sri Guru Tegh Bahadur Khalsa College, University of Delhi
Email: mansi@sgtbkhalsa.du.ac.in

Corresponding Author: Dr. Mansi Bansal

Article History

Received on: 21-Mar 2026

Revised on: 28-Mar-2026

Accepted on: 29- Apr 2026

First Published: 13-May-2026

Cite this Article as

Navika Jain, Parveen Kaur Lamba, & Mansi Bansal (2026), "the influence of online reviews and ratings on consumer purchase decisions of electronic accessories", *International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management*, Volume 14, Issue1, 2026,

DOI :

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20183260>

ABSTRACT

Online shopping has increased significantly especially after the coronavirus disease pandemic and it has altered the way individuals make decisions on what to purchase. Among the evident changes is that individuals now rely heavily on online reviews and ratings as consumers before they make a buying decision. This is primarily the case since when they do online shopping, they cannot look at or touch the product, prior to making a purchase decision.

It is further influential when it comes to electronic accessories such as earphones, power banks, chargers and speakers. Many similar options exist at practically the same price and, because these products cannot be checked physically, people learn about them through reading the reviews. They depend on each other so that they make a decision on what other buyers on the same product have posted.

Due to the ever-growing online shopping, it has become significant to know how reviews and ratings impact on buying decisions of people.

This paper will discuss the effects of internet reviews and ratings on people who purchase online-based electronic accessories with references to the people of the Delhi-NCR. It examines various factors, such as how important reviews are in general, the level of stars they receive, the number of reviews, whether the reviews are positive or negative, and how credible individuals find them. It also tests whether such variables as gender, age, employment, and income vary the extent to which individuals rely on reviews.

The study is based on descriptive research design and provides an online questionnaire to 202 of its respondents who live in the Delhi-NCR. The data was analysed with the help of the open-source programme, similar to the IBM SPSS, which is called GNU PSPP. Descriptive statistics, reliability analysis, simple linear regression, and one-way ANOVA are used to conduct the analysis.

The study adds to the existing research on electronic word-of-mouth and online consumer behaviour, while focusing on the under-explored product category of electronic accessories. The findings also offer many useful insights for online sellers and e-commerce platforms.

Keywords: Online Reviews, Star Ratings, Electronic Word-of-Mouth (e-WOM),

1. Introduction

Shopping has changed a lot in the last few years. With the internet growing so quickly, the way people find, compare, and buy products is very different now. Things that earlier needed a trip to the market can now be done from home in just a few minutes. With affordable smartphones, cheaper internet, and dozens of shopping apps like Amazon, Flipkart, and Meesho, online shopping has become a part of our everyday life.

While online shopping makes purchasing much more easier, it also brings some challenges. In online shopping, it is not possible for consumers to see, touch, or try a product before buying it. In a physical store, a consumer can pick up a product, see it closely, ask questions, and then make a choice. In online shopping, the consumer can only see a few photographs and read the description given by the seller. This is one of the biggest drawbacks of online shopping, and it is something that every consumer has experienced.

It is this problem that has made online reviews and ratings so important. When a consumer is unsure about a product, he turns to the views of other people who have already bought it. Customers who have used a product share their opinions and experiences on the internet in the form of reviews and ratings. These have become one of the most trusted sources of information for online shoppers.

Reviews and ratings serve different but complementary purposes. Reviews are descriptive - they help a consumer understand the actual experience of using a product, like quality, ease of use, value for money, and any problems the buyer faced. Ratings, on the other hand, are usually given in the form of stars on a five-point scale, and give an idea of overall customer satisfaction. Together, they provide an easy basis for consumers to evaluate a product they have never seen in person.

However, this is not a new concept in human behaviour. Even before the age of internet, people relied on the opinions of others for making purchase decisions. This was traditionally called word-of-mouth, and it was considered one of the most powerful marketing tools. This digital version of word-of-mouth is called Electronic Word-of-Mouth, or e-WOM.

Electronic accessories are everyday tech products like earphones, power banks, charging cables, bluetooth speakers, USB hubs, laptop stands, etc. They are used along with an electronic gadget like smartphone, television, laptop, etc. and cannot operate standalone. They are sold by hundreds of brands and at many price points, and cannot be compared based on photographs alone.

This study focuses on the Delhi-NCR region, which includes Delhi, Noida, Gurugram, Ghaziabad, and Faridabad. It has been selected because the internet penetration is high, online shopping is common and the people here are of different age groups, levels of income, and professions.

These aspects are all examined in the study but how much the reviews matter, the role star ratings play, the number of reviews, whether the reviews are positive or negative and how people assess their usefulness and trustworthiness. An online questionnaire was used to gather data of 202 individuals and then analysed in GNU PSPP.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Electronic Word-of-Mouth and Online Reviews

Customers would share their product experience with each other by use of word of mouth before the internet. They discussed among their friends, family and neighbours on what they purchased and what they liked and what they regretted. In the case of businesses this was one of the most powerful and cheapest marketing tools, and led to sales. The rapid growth and expansion of the internet changed this completely. As e-commerce and online shopping grew, a new kind of word-of-mouth emerged. This came to be called Electronic Word-of-Mouth, or e-WOM - when consumers share their product experiences online. Hennig-Thurau et al. (2004) defined e-WOM as any positive or negative statement made by a potential, actual, or former customer, about a product or company, over the internet.

Online ratings and reviews are the most common forms of e-WOM. Consumers who have used a product can share their opinions online through star ratings, written reviews, photos, or videos. Other consumers then use this information to decide whether to buy the product. Another advantage of e-WOM is its permanence. A review written by a buyer today can be read by a consumer even two years later. Unlike a conversation that happens and gets forgotten, online reviews stay on the platform and continue to influence purchase decisions long after they are written.

2.2 Star Ratings

Among all the elements that make up an online review system, star ratings are what a buyer sees first. They show up in search results even before a product page is opened. Lackermair et al. (2013) discovered that star ratings work as a quick low-effort shortcut for buyers, helping them filter through a large number of similar products with similar prices, without spending too much time and effort. Hu et al. (2014) shown that buyers tend to gravitate toward products rated 4 stars and above and that even a marginal drop in the average rating can significantly reduce the chances of making a purchase. A one-star improvement in average rating was demonstrated to produce a measurable lift in sales. This filtering function becomes even more relevant in electronic accessories.

2.3 Volume of Reviews

The number of reviews and rating that a product possesses will indicate the level of popularity of such a product. A product sitting at 4.29 stars with 578 reviews is likely to be

trusted more than one with a perfect five stars but only 13 reviews. This behaviour is rooted in what Cialdini (2001) described as social evidence, which is the tendency of people to look at what others have done as a guide for their own decisions, especially in situations of uncertainty. Duan et al. (2008) empirically established that volume of review drives sales independently of average rating since the greater the number of reviews, the greater the adoption and lesser the perceived risk of purchasing. For lesser-known brands operating in the electronic accessories market, a strong review count can go some way toward making up for the absence of brand recognition.

2.4 Review Valence

Review valence refers to whether the overall tone of reviews leans positive or negative. A well-established finding in consumer research is that negative reviews tend to carry more weight in purchase decisions than positive ones of equal strength, a pattern known as the negativity bias. Chevalier and Mayzlin(2006) found this to be true in the context of book sales, where negative reviews produced a stronger impact than comparable positive ones. Yin et al. (2023) found the difference to be sharper in cases where a poor purchase is difficult to reverse. Since electronic accessories are frequently non-returnable, a single complaint about durability or compatibility can differ the reassurance offered by many positive reviews. Lackermair et al. (2013) found that more than one in ten respondents reported that a single negative review was sufficient to make them abandon a purchase. That said, Lee and Youn (2009) observed an interesting counterpoint: a product with a small number of negative reviews mixed in among many positive ones can actually come across as more credible than one with nothing but praise, since perfectly uniform feedback tends to raise suspicion.

2.5 Review Credibility and Usefulness

A review only influences behavior if the reader trusts it. Corbitt et al. (2003) and Pavlou (2003) both identified consumer trust as a foundational condition for purchase completion in online settings. Several cues have been found to signal that a review is genuine. Tobing and Fernando (2025) discovered that reviews accompanied by images or videos are seen as more helpful and more credible than text-only reviews, largely because they show the actual product rather than the polished images provided by the seller. Mudambi and Schuff (2010)found that reviews which go into specific detail, covering features, advantages, and drawbacks, are rated as more useful than short, vague ones. Pathania et al. (2022) pointed out that the recency of a review matters too, since older reviews may not reflect the current version of a product or its manufacturing quality. Bickart and Schindler (2001) found that a verified buyer tag on a review substantially raises the level of trust a reader places in it.

2.6 Demographic Factors

Whether demographic factors change how much a person relies on online reviews is something researchers have not fully agreed on. Bae and Lee (2011) found that women paid

more attention to negative reviews than men did, and were more likely to change their purchase decision based on what those reviews said. Bickart and Schindler (2001) found that younger consumers leaned on reviews more heavily, partly because they had less prior experience with the products they were buying. Gurav et al. (2023) noted that older consumers tended to be more careful when reading reviews and were more likely to look for verified buyer indicators before trusting what they read. At the same time, several other studies have found no significant demographic differences in review at all, which suggests that checking online reviews before buying has simply become a common habit across all kinds of consumers, regardless of age, gender, or background.

2.7 Research Gap

The body of research on e-WOM and consumer behavior is quite large, but most of it has either focused on high-involvement purchases like smartphones, laptops, and hotel bookings, or has looked at products in general without zeroing in on any specific category. Electronic accessories, which are bought frequently, are available across hundreds of brands, and compete heavily on price, have not received much attention in this literature. On top of that, most existing studies have been carried out in Western or Chinese markets. India is a large and fast-growing e-commerce market with its own patterns of price sensitivity, customer trust, and buying behavior that have not been studied enough. This paper tries to fill both these gaps by focusing specifically on electronic accessories in the Delhi-NCR region, and by looking at four dimensions of reviews together.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Research Objectives

The main objective of this study is to understand how online reviews and ratings influence how consumers buy electronic accessories.

The specific objectives are:

1. To study how online reviews affect purchase decisions for electronic accessories.
2. To see how star ratings affect purchase decisions for electronic accessories.
3. To understand how the volume of reviews and ratings affects purchase decisions for electronic accessories.
4. To study how the tone of reviews (especially negative ones) affects purchase decisions for electronic accessories.
5. To understand how consumers see the usefulness and trustworthiness of online reviews for electronic accessories.
6. To determine whether demographic information such as gender, age, job and income influences how people rely on reviews and ratings when purchasing electronic accessories.

3.2 Research Hypotheses

H1: Online reviews play a major role in the consumer buying decision making indicating purchases of electronic accessories.

H2: The Star rating has a drastic impact in influencing the consumer buying behavior regarding the purchase of electronic accessories.

H3: The quantity of reviews influences consumer buying choices of electronic accessories significantly.

H4: Review valence plays a powerful role in consumer purchasing decisions of electronic accessories.

3.3 Research Design and Approach

This paper employs a quantitative approach to comprehend the influence that online reviews and ratings have on the decision that people make when purchasing electronic accessories. The primary data was gathered with the help of a questionnaire which was created on Google Forms.

The questionnaire was designed having the objectives of the study in mind. It consists of 23 questions, and it is organised in seven segments focusing on different aspects of how people use and trust online reviews.

The questionnaire has multiple choice questions as well as Likert scale questions, whereby a person could respond with either Strongly Agree, Strongly Disagree and so forth. The key variables in this investigation are the reviews and ratings and the purchase decision on purchasing electronic accessories is the outcome of this investigation.

3.4 Population and Sample

The population of this study covers consumers in the Delhi-NCR region, who have experience purchasing electronic accessories online. Delhi-NCR covers Delhi and its surrounding areas like Noida, Gurugram, Ghaziabad, and Faridabad. Given the large size of the population, it was not feasible to include every individual. Thus, a sample of 202 respondents from the Delhi-NCR region was selected for the study. Convenience sampling was used as the sampling technique for this study.

3.5 Data Analysis

The data collected through the questionnaire was analysed using GNU PSPP. The analysis involved the use of both, descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. Reliability testing was conducted using inferential analysis such as Cronbach's Alpha, simple linear regression, and one-way ANOVA were respectively used to test the hypothesis as well as to analyse the effect of demographic factors on the reliance on the review.

3.6 Reliability

Before performing statistical analysis, the reliability of the questionnaire is tested to make sure that the questions consistently measure what they are intended to measure. Cronbach's Alpha (α) was used for this purpose. The reliability analysis was run on all 17 multiple-choice and Likert-scale items (Questions 7 to 23) using GNU PSPP. The Cronbach's Alpha value came out to be 0.950, which falls in the 'excellent' range ($\alpha \geq 0.90$). This shows a high degree of internal consistency among the questions. It confirms that the data collected is suited for further analysis.

4. Results and Findings

All analysis was carried out using GNU PSPP. Simple linear regression was used to test each of the four hypotheses. Independent and dependent variables were decided as the review dimension and purchase decision respectively. Model fit was evaluated using R^2 and the F-statistic. One-way ANOVA was used to check whether review reliance varied across demographic groups, covering gender, age, occupation, and monthly household income. A significance level of 0.05 was applied throughout.

4.1 Demographic Profile

Most of the people in the study - 78.7% (159 out of 202) - are in the 18-24 age group. The next biggest group is 25–34 years, making up 11.4% (23 people). Those aged 45 and above make up 5% (10 people), followed by those below 18 years at 2% (4 people), and 35–44 years at 3% (6 people).

Out of the 202 people in the study, 58.9% (119) were male and 41.1% (83) were female.

Occupation-wise, the highest population was found to be among the students (56.4% (114 people)). Employees at 27.7% (56 people) followed by business owners at 12.4%. The 2% (4 people) was teaching professionals and the remaining 1.5% (3 people) belonged to other occupations such as advocate, writer, and artist.

Approximately, 43.6 percent (88 individuals) who declined to declare their monthly household earnings. The highest earning rate, 30.2% (61 people) said that they earned more than 125,000 per month. Around 11.4% (23 people) said their income was below ₹50,000. The rest were spread across ₹50,000–₹75,000 (6.4%), ₹75,000–₹1,00,000 (3.5%), and ₹1,00,000–₹1,25,000 (5.0%).

37.6% (76 people) - make purchases online every now and again, i.e., once in 4-6 months. Another group of buyers follows, but once in every 2-3 months at 27.2% (55 people).

72.8% (147 people) of them said they use both star ratings and written reviews when purchasing online electronic accessories.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

Construct	Item	Mean	SD	% Agree
Online Reviews	Read reviews before buying	2.04	1.22	67.8%
Online Reviews	Reviews influence decisions	2.23	1.25	65.8%
Star Ratings	Prefer highly rated products	2.08	1.16	69.8%
Review Volume	Trust products with many reviews	2.06	1.14	69.3%
Review Valence	Negative reviews matter more	2.18	1.15	68.0%

The average scores of all the 17 questions are lower than the mid-point of 3 on the five-point scale. None of the items provided a mean over 3.0, indicating that the respondents are in agreement that reviews and ratings do affect their online purchase behaviour.

Question (22) (“Reviews with photos or videos are more helpful than text-only reviews”) had the lowest average a score in the entire study of 1.960 and greatest level of agreement of 71.3%. Question 9 asked if respondents trust online reviews more than product descriptions. It showed a mean of 2.505 and the weakest agreement at 49.5%

4.3 Hypothesis Testing

All four research hypotheses were tested using simple linear regression, and all four were accepted

Hypothesis	Beta	Sig. Value	Result
H1 Online Reviews	0.14	<0.05	Supported
H2 Star Ratings	0.562	<0.01	Supported
H3 Review Volume	0.548	<0.01	Supported
H4 Review Valence	0.5	<0.05	Supported

4.4 H1 - Influence of Online Reviews

The regression model reveals that the value of R is 0.140 and the value of R square = 0.019. This implies that the relation between online reviews and purchase decisions has a positive, yet weak correlation. The review factor only has an R squared of 0.019 which means that reviews alone can only explain 1.9 per cent change in purchasing decision of electronic accessories. It gave an F value of 3.938 and a significance value of 0.049. As this is less than 0.05 the number is deemed significant.

Based on these results, H1 is accepted. Indeed, online reviews can have a significant impact on the purchasing decision of electronic accessories. Nevertheless, the low value of R square (0.019) and just significant p-value (0.049) demonstrate that this effect is not as large when considering reviews alone.

4.5 H2 - Impact of Star Ratings

This hypothesis showed the strongest results in the entire study. The regression analysis gave an R value of 0.562 and an R Square value of 0.316. This implies that the positive relationship between ratings of stars and purchase decisions is strong. The value of the R square

at 0.316 indicates that the change in purchase decisions of electronic accessories is explainable only by the value of the R square used.

The test gave an F value of 62.830 and a significance value of 0.000 ($p < 0.001$). This result is very solid and is a clear indication that the association between star rankings and buying decisions is significant.

Based on these results, H2 is accepted. Star ratings exhibit significant and substantial influence to purchase decision with respect to the purchase of electronic accessories.

4.6 H3 - Role of Review Volume

This hypothesis showed the second strongest effect in the study. The regression analysis gave an R value of 0.548 and an R Square value of 0.300. This implies that the change in the buying decision can be explained by a fraction of about 30% of the number of reviews. This is a good score and incredibly close to what we had observed with star ratings (31.6%).

The ANOVA table gave an F value of 86.000 and a significance of 0.000 ($p < 0.001$). This is the largest F value of all the hypotheses, which means that this is a very powerful and consistent result.

On the results of the same, H3 is accepted. The quantity of reviews and ratings significantly and significantly influence the purchase decisions of electronic accessories

4.7 H4 - Effect of Review Valence

Review valence, meaning whether the tone of reviews is positive or negative, was also found to have a significant association with purchase decisions. The regression results gave a value of $R = .500$ and a value of $R^2 = 0.250$. This implies that the tone of reviews (positive or negative) elucidates 25% of the change in buying decisions. It also reveals clearly that the sound of reviews has a potent impact upon the choice of the people to buy a certain product.

The ANOVA table gave an F value of 64.020 and a significance value of 0.000 ($p < 0.001$). This implies that the outcome will be extremely robust, and definitely not random.

The Coefficients table (Table 17) shows a B value of 0.430, a Beta of 0.500, and a t-value of 7.990 ($p = 0.000$). The positive Beta indicates that as the reviews become more positive, people would be more likely to purchase the product.

Based on these results, H4 is accepted. The effect of a review valence on buying electronic accessories is clear and meaningful.

4.8 Review Credibility and Usefulness

I find long and detailed reviews more trustworthy than short and generic reviews

202 responses

Question 21 enquired whether individuals have more confidence in long, detailed written reviews so compared to short reviews. 57.4 percent respondents agreed with this statement.

Reviews with attached pictures or videos of the product are more helpful than text reviews.

202 responses

Question 22 recorded the best score in the entire study. It questioned whether reviews including photos or videos are more helpful compared to those reviews which include text only. A majority of the respondents (144 out of 200) agreed with the view (71.3%), the highest agreement rate in the study. Mean score of 1.960 is also the lowest with a very strong agreement achieved overall.

I consider recent online reviews more relevant and useful than older reviews

202 responses

Question 23 questioned how people believe that publicity that was posted in the recent past is more productive as compared to but not limited to old ones. 55.9% of respondents (113 people) agreed, with an average score of 2.342.

4.9 Demographic Analysis

One-way ANOVA was run across gender, age group, occupation, and monthly household income to check whether review reliance looked different across these groups. No statistically significant differences were found for any of the four demographic variables. This shows that relying on online reviews and ratings when purchasing electronic accessories is a broadly shared behaviour within this sample, and is not shaped by demographic characteristics. Whether a respondent is male or female, young or older, student or employee, or from a lower or higher income household, they show a similar level of reliance on online reviews and ratings when shopping for electronic accessories.

5. Practical Implications

The greatest lesson is to online sellers of electronic accessories. The analysis indicates that the quantity of reviews that a product receives - its star rating, number of reviews, and what people say in them - is a significant factor in determining whether or not a person purchases it.

The most significant factor was found to be the star ratings. Because 87.6% of the people indicated that they will not even think about a product that is less than 4.0 stars. This implies that the sellers will have to concentrate on maintaining their ratings at high levels.

The second factor that was the most important was the number of reviews. Although a product might have good rating, with very few reviews, people may get unsure about a product. Sellersought to motivate satisfied customers to leave a review. It is achievable by following up messages, little notes in the package, or a reminder upon delivery.

The negative reviews are significant too. Because 68.8% of the surveyed people affirmed that they changed their mind after reading an unfavorable review, sellers must learn how to deal with them. Instead of deleting them, it is better to respond in an amicable and fast manner or accept the problem but explain how this problem is being corrected. A seller, who has a good response to it, is more likely than someone that has merely perfect reviews and no reply. Performing the fix on the actual issue, such as quality, misdescription, and packaging, and mentioning it in the response can help to mitigate the effect of a bad review.

One more essential aspect is that an individual takes a review with a photo or a video more useful. Sellers must request customers to include pictures or videos in their reviews. The platforms should also be easy to post pictures and videos, and bring out the top ones in the review section.

6. Limitations and Future Scope

The study has some limitations that can be taken care of in future researches. Some suggestions are given below.

Future studies can use a larger and more diverse sample. This study had 202 respondents from Delhi-NCR, most of whom were students aged 18 - 24 years old. A larger sample, spread across different cities, age groups, income levels and occupations could be used.

Future researches could also cover other cities and regions of India. Delhi-NCR is an urban, digitally active market. Consumer behaviour may be very different in smaller cities and towns.

In this research, electronic accessories were the only centers of interest. Future researches have the possibility of investigating other forms of products to understand whether reviews and ratings have the same or different significance.

Future research may also address directly to individuals via interviews or group discussion. In this research, a questionnaire was employed and this is good because it gives clear responses, but it does not present how people think when reading reviews.

7. Conclusion

This research paper examined the impact of reviews, and ratings on individuals purchasing electronic accessories over the internet. It took data related to 202 individuals in the area of Delhi-NCR. The study hypotheses were all accepted. Star ratings had the greatest impact of all the factors. Actually, 87.6 percent of individuals replied they would never notion of purchasing a product with a rating less than 4.0 stars. The next factor that had significance was review volume. The more reviews towards the product, the greater the level of trust attached. The tone of the reviews also influenced - there was a stronger influence of negative reviews than

positive ones. The most beneficial reviews that included photos or videos were observed to be the most helpful and the highest level of agreement noted in the study at 71.3%. No significant difference was noticed in the demographic factors such as gender, age, job, and income. Finally, this paper demonstrates that reviews and ratings have a strong impact on the purchasing decision-making process related to electronic accessories in India.

References

- Bae, S., & Lee, T. (2011). Product type and consumers' perception of online consumer reviews. *Electronic Markets*, 21(4), 255-266.
- Bickart, B., & Schindler, R. M. (2001). Internet forums as influential sources of consumer information. *Journal of interactive marketing*, 15(3), 31-40.
- Chevalier, J. A., & Mayzlin, D. (2006). The effect of word of mouth on sales: Online book reviews. *Journal of marketing research*, 43(3), 345-354.
- Cialdini, R. (2001). Principles of persuasion. *Arizona State University, eBrand Media Publication*, 3(7), 2580-2592.
- Corbitt, B. J., Thanasankit, T., & Yi, H. (2003). Trust and e-commerce: a study of consumer perceptions. *Electronic commerce research and applications*, 2(3), 203-215.
- Duan, W., Gu, B., & Whinston, A. B. (2008). Do online reviews matter?—An empirical investigation of panel data. *Decision support systems*, 45(4), 1007-1016.
- Gurav, Y., Ingawale, V., & Yadav, A. (2023). A study on the impact of online product reviews on consumers' buying intentions. *The Online Journal of Distance Education and e-Learning*, 11(2), 1924-1928.
- Hennig-Thurau, T., Gwinner, K. P., Walsh, G., & Gremler, D. D. (2004). Electronic word-of-mouth via consumer-opinion platforms: what motivates consumers to articulate themselves on the internet?. *Journal of interactive marketing*, 18(1), 38-52.
- Hu, N., Koh, N. S., & Reddy, S. K. (2014). Ratings lead you to the product, reviews help you clinch it? The mediating role of online review sentiments on product sales. *Decision support systems*, 57, 42-53.
- Lackermair, G., Kailer, D., & Kanmaz, K. (2013). Importance of online product reviews from a consumer's perspective. *Advances in economics and business*, 1(1), 1-5.
- Lee, M., & Youn, S. (2009). Electronic word of mouth (eWOM) How eWOM platforms influence consumer product judgement. *International journal of advertising*, 28(3), 473-499.
- Mudambi, S. M., & Schuff, D. (2010). Research note: What makes a helpful online review? A study of customer reviews on Amazon.com. *MIS quarterly*, 185-200.
- Pathania, A., Dixit, S., & Rasool, G. (2022). 'Are online reviews the new shepherd?'—examining herd behaviour in wearable technology adoption for personal healthcare. *Journal of Marketing Communications*, pp.1-27.

- Pavlou, P. A. (2003). Consumer acceptance of electronic commerce: Integrating trust and risk with the technology acceptance model. *International journal of electronic commerce*, 7(3), 101-134.
- Tobing, P. Y., & Fernando, A. (2025). Exploring the influence of product variety, customer reviews, and promotions on purchase decisions: A study on Shopee Indonesia. *International Journal of Family Business Practices*, 7(2), 104-121.
- Yin, D., de Vreede, T., Steele, L. M., & de Vreede, G. J. (2023). Decide now or later: Making sense of incoherence across online reviews. *Information Systems Research*, 34(3), 1211-1227.